

Effects of cultural, economic and institutional factors on entrepreneurial activityⁱ

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Abstract

This research aims to analyze the cultural, institutional, and economic factors that affect entrepreneurial activity. For this, the possible variations of existing effects were highlighted when considering the motivation to become an entrepreneur (opportunity/necessity) in emerging countries such as the Federative Republic of Brazil. In this sense, a linear regression model was chosen with panel data as a method of data analysis. According to the results, entrepreneurship in Brazil can be better explained by formal economic and institutional factors than by cultural variables. As main conclusions, the discovered results contribute to the literature in contemplating the multidimensionality of entrepreneurship, which, having determinants from different spheres of analysis, invite the research to relate interdisciplinary factors to advance the understanding of this phenomenon. This reinforces the analysis model used with potential application in entrepreneurship policy, including in other countries.

Keywords: Economy. Culture. Institutions. Development. Public Policy.

Introduction

Economics research literature has long described explanatory factors for the growing gap between nations (Solow, 1956, Swan, 1956). Such surveys provide insight into the paths to be taken to cope with recessions marked by low employment and income rates. In this process, in addition to showing traditional economic variables (such as investment rate and government spending), some studies have included new significant factors to explain production levels between economies (Acemoglu *et al.*, 2014; Lucas, 1988; Rodrik, 2003; Romer, 1986).

Authors such as Audretsch and Thurik (2000), Audretsch, Grilo and Thurik (2007), Thurik, Wennekers and Uhlaner (2002) present empirical evidence on the importance of entrepreneurship in achieving high levels of economic growth. The first edition of the report on Entrepreneurial Activity - 1999 *Global Entrepreneurship Monitor* (GEM) highlights three positive consequences of entrepreneurship for the nations' economy, as well as solid economic prosperity (particularly Gross Domestic Product) measures; new businesses tend to contribute substantially to increasing employment and to the competitiveness of countries in the international market (Reynolds *et al.*, 1999).

In this context, scientific efforts are made to identify factors that encourage entrepreneurship in economies (Lundström & Stevenson, 2005; Verheul *et al.*, 2002; Wennekers, Uhlaner, & Thurik, 2002), as well as understand the motivations of individuals to become entrepreneurs. Thus, the research question arises: which factors (cultural, institutional and economic) affect entrepreneurship (entrepreneurial activity)?

This is not a new issue in entrepreneurship studies, while it is current, due to the peculiarities of each country, as they may vary over time. This makes periodical studies on this subject relevant. Macedo *et al.* (2014) point to at least two primary reasons for the entrepreneurship decision: they are by necessity (when there are no employment alternatives) or by opportunity (when an opportunity is identified for a new business in the market). Tan (2002) and Wong *et al.* (2005) indicate that entrepreneurship by opportunity is more correlated to high economic growth, while entrepreneurship by necessity, with lower growth rates, is more present in emerging economies. This context can be evidenced in the Brazilian case.

According to the 2015 GEM report, the country has a high Total early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity (TEA) compared to other nations with a similar or higher level of development. However, such growth, achieved in a recession (2014-2015), is due to necessity and social vulnerability, probably them still nowadays. This situation reveals that the decision for entrepreneurship in Brazil may be assuming less dependence on economic performance, being influenced by other factors (Macedo *et al.*, 2014).

In this context, to understand the variation of entrepreneurial activity (due to opportunity and necessity) in Brazil and its possible diversification in national territory, this article proposes analyzing the institutional, cultural, and economic factors that affect entrepreneurial activity in the Brazilian states.

It is understood that highlighting factors that lead to entrepreneurship is a relevant practice for the formulation of public policies that stimulate entrepreneurship (Castaño, Méndez, & Galindo, 2015), especially in emerging economic contexts, as suggested in the literature (Aparicio *et al.*, 2016, Mohamad *et al.*, 2021, Urbano & Alvarez, 2014).

Literature review: Institutional, cultural, economic and entrepreneurship factors

The search for understanding the determinants of differences in entrepreneurship between countries and regions has become an effort of some theorists (Carree *et al.*, 2002, Verheul *et al.*, 2002; Wennerkes *et al.*, 2002). Verheul *et al.* (2002) point to an eclectic and interdisciplinary nature of the phenomenon of entrepreneurship, which encompasses geographic, financial, administrative, sociological, political and other aspects. The authors emphasize that the determinants of the level of entrepreneurship of society are multifactorial.

In the same sense, the OECD (1998) states that there is not only a single set of causes to determine the increase or decrease in the number of entrepreneurs in society. Conversely, several technological, economic, institutional and cultural factors influence entrepreneurial activity among individuals. These papers highlight the relevance of understanding the factors that may affect entrepreneurial activity in formulating public policies to stimulate entrepreneurship.

Based on the literature, it is possible to highlight at least three different levels of analysis on entrepreneurship determinants. At the micro-level, the works are aimed at understanding the decision of the individuals to become entrepreneurs or not (Blanchflower, 2000); at the meso level, the research studies the specific determinants of the market, such as profit opportunities, and finally, at the macro level, the papers that combine the arguments of the micro and meso approach are concentrated to build a perspective on a series of environmental factors (Carree *et al.*, 2002), as is the case of cultural, institutional and economic variables discussed in the present study.

Institutional factors assume the concept presented by North (1990), which defines institutions as the rules of the game in a society, more specifically, as the mechanisms of contrition that shape social interactions. For this author and contemporaries, Ronald Coase, Elinor Ostrom and Oliver Williamson, who consolidated the New Institutional Economy (NEI), individuals tend to develop behavioral rules, that is, institutions, to minimize the uncertainties between human interactions (Bueno, 2011). This premise endeavored to understand social interactions and their economic unfolding, which is presumed, in this study, as an element of influence on the entrepreneurial activity in the Brazilian states.

As evidenced by some authors, institutional factors influence the level of entrepreneurship (Aidis *et al.*, 2008; Alvarez & Urbano, 2011; Salimath & Cullen, 2010). In this context, institutions are divided into two main categories by the literature: formal institutions and informal institutions.

Formal institutions are contracts, procedures, government policies, access to credit, financial assistance, non-financial assistance, and other societal elements. They reflect their values, translating them into laws and regulatory standards. Informal institutions, in turn, are more related to social conditions, such as the trust of individuals and their perception of the environment in which they are located (North, 1990). In this paper, formal institutions such as access to credit and the tax burden will be considered, factors of recognized importance to understand entrepreneurship (Aparicio *et al.*, 2016; Melo, Sampaio, & Oliveira, 2015).

Some studies relate this variable to individual decisions by entrepreneurship (Audretsch & Grilo, Thurik, 2007; Verheul *et al.*, 2002). Lundstrom and Stevenson (2006) and Reynolds *et al.* (1999) highlight the role of culture in developing attitudes towards entrepreneurship through education and empowerment of individuals. Higher educational rates tend to favor entrepreneurship by increasing the likelihood of individuals with skills necessary for the exercise of entrepreneurship.

Verheul *et al.* (2002) emphasize that resources, skills, personal characteristics, and preferences are the main inputs for accessing and analyzing the costs and benefits of the entrepreneurial opportunity to alternative occupational opportunities. In this context, the role of culture enables individuals to entrepreneurship and induces their preferences against the employment options of their workforce.

Nevertheless, education is not the only cultural element influencing entrepreneurship. Authors point to a positive variation between an environment endowed with pro-entrepreneurship values and the level of self-employment of a society (Wilken, 1979; Wildeman *et al.*, 1999), as well as the positive relationship between a culture that legitimizes entrepreneurship and the number of entrepreneurs involved (Casson, 2010).

The level of corruption among countries is also considered among cultural factors. Its effects on entrepreneurship are contradictory. El Harbi and Anderson (2010) signal a positive correlation between bureaucratic corruption and entrepreneurship. Dreher and Gassebner (2013) and Melo, Sampaio and Oliveira (2015) reveal a positive relationship between the two variables, especially in environments with excessive regulation. On the other hand, Ovaska and Sobel (2005) show a negative correlation between bureaucratic corruption and entrepreneurial activity in European countries. In a study on Brazil, Carraro *et al.* (2011) emphasize the results of these authors, underlining a significant relationship between entrepreneurship and corruption.

Much of the interest of governments in fostering entrepreneurship is due to expectations of returns in employment and income in the economy. The causal relationship between entrepreneurial activity and economic performance is still controversial in the academic literature. This feature offers endogeneity to the analytical models that involve this phenomenon (Melo *et al.*, 2015). This context, however, does not constitute a barrier to explanatory efforts in this sense.

For decades entrepreneurship has been neglected in the models inspired by the neoclassical theory of economic growth (Lundström & Stevenson, 2006); the rise of the endogenous growth model in the early 1990s, in turn, repositioned entrepreneurship as an essential variable for economic growth among countries (Carree *et al.* 2002).

Studies, such as Carree *et al.* (2002), indicate the existence of a U-graph that relates economic growth and entrepreneurial activity; Castaño *et al.* (2015) as well as Galindo and Méndez (2014), in contrast, point to a positive relationship between entrepreneurship and economic growth. Shane (2009) and Morris, Neumeyer, Kuratko. (2015) signifies the different relationships between the type of entrepreneurship established and the economic growth of localities, countries, and regions.

In Brazil, its history is demarcated by different forms of colonization, highlighting diverse priorities for regional development (Diniz, 2002). While the South and Southeast intensified in industrial expansion and transportation, the North and Midwest took longer

to realize these investments and hampered the development process of these regions. Although more than 500 years after the discovery of Brazil, this situation did not reduce inequalities, with the South and Southeast regions having better levels of education and income, while the Northeast region has the worst indicators in these areas (Lima & Sousa, 2014).

Research Method

The main objective of this paper is to identify the various cultural, institutional, and economic factors that affect entrepreneurship, highlighting the possible variations of existing effects when considering the motivation to become an entrepreneur (opportunity/necessity). For this, a linear regression model was chosen with panel data as a method of data analysis. It is understood that the use of panel data offers a series of advantages over other statistical models when considering this research proposal.

A relevant factor in applying this method is the expansion of the observations to be considered. Panel data are composed of individual information varying over time, increasing the degree of freedom. This feature presents a great advantage of this method, considering the limited number of observations for the Brazilian states (27) when considering a cross-sectional analysis model. Thus, in addition to providing more information and data variability, panel models lead to less multicollinearity, greater freedom, and consequently, enhanced reliability, efficiency, and robustness of the proposed model (Marques, 2000; Wooldridge, 2010), justifying its suitability to meet the theoretical expectations of the present research.

The data referring to 2001-2012 was selected, given the 27 federative units' sample, the Brazilian states, and the Federal District. This period was chosen according to public data available for the variables listed here and because the following results of the National Census are only predicted after 2022. The attempt was to estimate three simple regression models, with the dependent variable as difference: (i) Initial entrepreneurship rate; (ii) initial entrepreneurship rate per opportunity; (iii) initial entrepreneurship rate by necessity. The panel model developed in this article can be described in its basic form by Expression 1.

$$\theta_{it} = \gamma_i + \gamma_1 \varepsilon_{it} + \gamma_2 \omega_{it} + \gamma_3 \varphi_{it} + \gamma_4 \beta_{it} + u_{it} \quad (1)$$

Wherein that represents the T by opportunity, necessity, or both;

γ_i is the model constant for each state i;

γ_n is the angular coefficient of the variables to be estimated;

ε_{it} represents economic factors for each state i and in year t;

ω_{it} represents institutional factors for each state i and in year t;

φ_{it} represents cultural factors for each state i and in year t;

β_{it} represents the dummies of regions for each state i and in year t;

u_{it} is the term of the template error

The variables represented in the model are described in Table 1, whose sources are predominantly data and public documents available on the internet in Brazilian public organizations, which are used for management and public policies (Garcia et al, 2016).

Table 1. Description and source of the survey data.

	Variable	Description	Source
Entrepreneurship	TEA	Percentage (%) of the population (18 - 64 years) born or new entrepreneurs.	GEM Brazil
	OE	Percentage (%) of the population (18-64) involved in entrepreneurship not because they have no other work option but because they have identified a business opportunity they wanted to pursue.	GEM Brazil
	NE	Percentage (%) of the population (18-64 years old) that is involved with entrepreneurship because they have no other work option	GEM Brazil
Economics	GDP	Gross National Product per capita, measured in R\$ 1,000.00.	IPEA
	EAP	Percentage of EAP per rural or urban domicile situation.	IBGE
	Gin	Gin index of household income per capita.	DATASUS
	UR	The unemployment rate of the economically active population (16 to 65 years).	PNAD (IBGE)
Institution	GTB	Gross tax burden.	Federal Revenue of Brazil
	Cre	Credit operations of the financial system -Total-P physical - R\$ (millions)	Central Bank of Brazil
Cultural	ed0-1	Percentage of EAP per education in average years of study - 0 to 1 year.	IBGE
	ed15+	Percentage of EAP per education in average years of study - 15 or more years	IBGE
	CI	General Corruption Index by state	Boll (2010)
Region	North	Binary variable, being 0 for State that does not belong to the North region, and 1 for which it belongs	IBGE
	Northeast	Binary variable, being 0 for State that does not belong to the Northeast region, and 1 for which it belongs	IBGE
	Southeast	Binary variable, being 0 for State that does not belong to the Southeast region, and 1 for which it belongs	IBGE
	South	Binary variable, being 0 for State that does not belong to the South region, and 1 for which it belongs	IBGE

Source: Prepared by the authors

Among the variables presented, it is necessary to calculate the tax burden (TB) and the General Corruption Index (CI) by state explicit, which present peculiarities about the others. It was sought to define the tax debut because of the tax collection on the State GDP; this calculation is in line with the Union Court of Auditors (Melo *et al.*, 2015).

In turn, the corruption index (CI) is defined according to the results of Boll (2010), which seeks to meet the need to create an index that measures bureaucratic corruption

among Brazilian states. For this, it is necessary to calculate the average between: $[(\text{CADIRREG value} / \text{standardized population}) + (\text{Standard CADIRREG} / \text{GDP}), (\text{Standard CADIRREG} / \text{LOA value})]$ and $(\text{Annual number of irregular CADIRREG cases by State} / \text{Total annual number of irregular CADIRREG cases})$.

Where CADIRREG represents the amount of State Accounts Deemed as irregular by the Court (TCU), the standard population is the population of each state, according to the IBGE in the period. GDP is the Gross Domestic Product at current prices by states, presented by IPEA. Finally, standardized LOA refers to the value of the resources of the Annual Budget Law for each Brazilian State and the Federal District. Thus, it is possible to construct an index of bureaucratic corruption for Brazilian federal units (Boll, 2010; Melo *et al.*, 2015).

Four binary variables were inserted as well, one for each region of Brazil. Although Brazil has five regions, it was decided to omit the Mid-West region. The constant of the model is capturing it.

It is understood that, in the model constructed in this study, the past Total early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity (whether by necessity, opportunity, or both) is relevant to explain the present rates. This is due to the possible effects of the number of entrepreneurs in society to encourage other individuals to entrepreneurship. This perspective is supported by Lundström and Stevenson (2006), who point to the positive effect of entrepreneurship exposure on the emergence of new entrepreneurs in society. In this sense, it was opted to include a lag of one (1) year for the entrepreneurship variables present in the model. There is, therefore, the establishment of a dynamic panel, which can be characterized by: (i) inclusion of past values of the dependent variable to explain itself; (ii) the heterogeneity in the variable and the dependent variable (s) independently and / or (iii) the heterogeneity occurs when not observed, the personal effect that varies over time (Cameron & Triverdi, 2009).

Theoretical evidence also shows endogeneity in the relationship between Gross Domestic Product (GDP) variables and unemployment rate with entrepreneurship rates (Prieger *et al.*, 2016; Smith, Chimucheka, 2014; Verheul *et al.*, 2002). Thus, it is considered that the endogeneity exists in the very dynamic character of the model, expressed by the lag of entrepreneurship rates as explanatory variables. The model is estimated by the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) that this study will be the model for short panels, System GMM, given the 26 Brazilian states and the Federal District for twelve (12) years.

According to Cangussu, Salvato and Nakabashi (2010), System GMM hypothesizes the non-correlation between the first difference instrument and the fixed effect, which increases the number of tools and their efficiency. To test the validation of the tools, the Sargan Test is used, as well as the Arellano-Bond test for serial autocorrelation of the errors in the first difference.

Results

Having performed the methodological procedures previously described, it was possible to obtain results that demonstrate some factors responsible for the variation of the entrepreneurship rates among the Brazilian states, including the Federal District. It is

worth mentioning, firstly, as can be seen in Figure 1, that the average rates of entrepreneurship vary considerably among the federative units in the period studied, with the state of São Paulo being the unit with the highest average Total early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity (mTEA) presenting itself as a highlight against other units of the Brazilian federation.

Figure 1. Average rates of entrepreneurship between the Brazilian states and the Federal District

Note: mNE, mOE, mTEA correspond to the average of the respective initial entrepreneurship rates (TEA), entrepreneurship by necessity (NE), and entrepreneurship by opportunity (OE) calculated for each Brazilian federal unit in the period 2001-2012.

The average Total early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity (mTEA) in the state of São Paulo was approximately three times higher than the rates in the states of Rio de Janeiro and Minas Gerais, followed by the second and third highest average rates in the period under analysis. It should be noted that the composition of the Total early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity (TEA) is given by the set of Necessity Entrepreneurship (NE) and Opportunity Entrepreneurship (OE) rates. Considering their averages for the period studied, a more significant proportion of entrepreneurs can be seen per opportunity entering the Brazilian market than entrepreneurs motivated by necessity.

Aparicio *et al.* (2016) emphasize the benefits of a greater composition of entrepreneurship by the opportunity for the Latin American countries; the authors highlight the potential of reducing unemployment and expanding economic activity. Wennekers *et al.* (2005), in turn, indicate that higher rates of necessity entrepreneurship are characteristic of the entrepreneurship compositions of underdeveloped countries.

In this sense, the distribution of entrepreneurship rates according to the motivations for necessity and opportunity in Brazil goes back to a period of pro-cyclical growth of total entrepreneurship among Brazilian states, a result consistent with Macedo *et al.* (2014), noting a similar behavior when analyzing Brazilian entrepreneurship between 2002 and 2012. This was a period favorable to the country's economic development as a whole.

Brazil's average initial entrepreneurship rate is mainly concentrated in the number of enterprising entrepreneurs in the markets of three southeastern states (São Paulo, Rio de Janeiro, and Minas Gerais) and two Brazilian states. region (Rio Grande do Sul and Paraná). In contrast, the lowest average initial entrepreneurship rate comes from Tocantins, Amapá, Acre, and Roraima, which belong to the country's northern region.

The discrepancy between the rates of entrepreneurship in the Brazilian regions may be related to the economic, cultural, and institutional multidimensions that characterize these territories. Identifying the various factors of influence on entrepreneurship can contribute to analyzing this context. Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics of the variables used in the present study.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs.	Average	Standard deviation	Min.	Max.
Tea	324	0.501	0.885	0.011	5.792
OE	324	0.289	0.526	0.006	3.939
NE	324	0.205	0.368	0.005	2.595
GDP	324	2.560	0.504	1.600	4.076
EAP	324	13.930	7.476	0.000	31.290
Gin	324	0.543	0.040	0.421	0.630
UR	324	8.873	2.633	3.145	20.539
GTB	324	0.072	0.030	0.022	0.179
Cre	324	15.038	1.647	11.106	19.539
Ed0-1	324	6.844	3.721	1.450	18.160
Ed15+	324	4.693	2.400	0.085	15.917
CI	324	0.313	0.270	0	1

Source: Prepared by the authors.

Table 2 indicates an average Total early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity (TEA) of 0.501 for all Brazilian states, with the average rate of Opportunity Entrepreneurship (OE) higher than the rate of Necessity Entrepreneurship (NE), corroborating the previously written arguments. There were 324 observations for all variables. This uniformity is due to the panel balancing procedures adopted in the present study. These consisted of applying the temporal growth rate of the variables for each federative unit, thus supplying the absence of some annual information. The individual credit values were submitted to a logarithmic function to smooth their effects in the regression due to the low maximum and minimum values of the other variables included in the model.

The three regressions estimated in this research contemplated the effects of cultural, institutional, and economic factors on entrepreneurship, trying simultaneously to understand the relations between dependent variables and the motivations (necessity or opportunity) to be undertaken in the Brazilian states (Table 3).

Table 3. Effects of cultural, institutional, and economic variables on entrepreneurship.

Factors	Variables	TEA	OE	NE	
Economics	L1.	0.953*** (0.033)	0.983*** (0.042)	0.806*** (0.073)	
	GDP	0.747* (0.410)	0.634* (0.361)	-0.020 (0.046)	
	L1.	-1.407** (0.576)	-1.024** (0.423)	-0.296* (0.150)	
	L2.	2.168** (1.011)	1.243** (0.569)	0.695** (0.312)	
	L3.	-1.444* (0.778)	-0.765* (0.434)	-0.457** (0.029)	
	EAP	-0.003 (0.004)	-0.001 (0.002)	-0.001 (0.001)	
	Gin	-0.167 (0.244)	-0.190 (0.192)	-0.054 (0.097)	
	UR	0.006 (0.007)	-0.001 (0.003)	0.005 (0.004)	
	L1.	-0.006 (0.004)	-0.003 (0.003)	-0.002* (0.001)	
	L2.	-0.012 (0.007)	-0.011* (0.006)	0.001 (0.002)	
	L3.	0.009* (0.005)	0.006* (0.005)	0.003 (0.002)	
	Institutional	GTB	-2.170* (1.191)	-0.846 (0.592)	-0.915* (0.505)
		L1.	0.430 (2.161)	1.646 (1.196)	0.993 (1.039)
L2.		-1.163 (1.186)	-0.760 (1.175)	-0.598 (0.602)	
Cre		0.007* (0.004)	-0.009** (0.004)	0.016*** (0.005)	
Cultural	Ed0-1	0.006 (0.009)	0.001 (0.005)	0.002 (0.003)	
	Ed15+	0.008 (0.006)	0.003 (0.007)	0.008 (0.006)	
	CI	0.032 (0.052)	0.047 (0.054)	-0.014 (0.010)	

Region	North	0.078 (0.055)	0.022 (0.028)	-0.008 (0.025)
	Northeast	0.099* (0.056)	0.076* (0.045)	-0.040 (0.045)
	Southeast	0.141 (0.144)	0.086 (0.094)	0.151 (0.125)
	South	0.050 (0.072)	0.013 (0.037)	0.027 (0.032)
	Const.	-0.270 (0.229)	0.003 (0.106)	-0.049 (0.098)
N° of Observations		243	243	243
Prob>Chi2		0.000***	0.000***	0.000***
Sargan (<i>p-value</i>)		0.229	0.071*	0.498
Arellano-Bond (<i>z-calc</i>)		0.143	0.150	0.168

Source: Prepared by the authors. Note: (***) level of significance at 1%, (**) level of significance at 5%. (*) level of significance at 10%. Estimates with robust standard errors. Corresponding default error in parentheses.

The estimated models were validated as a whole, as evidenced by the significance of Chi2 tests. In addition, the instruments used were adequate for the estimation of regressions in system GMM, considering the results of the Sargan Test, which accepted the null hypothesis in all the estimates at a 5% level, thus validating the instruments in the model.

In addition to the lags of the dependent variables under analysis, which confers the dynamic character of the model, three lags were included on the GDP variables per capita (GDP), unemployment rate (UR), and tax burden (TB) since their variables would influence the present decision for entrepreneurship.

Discussions

Given the presented results, it is possible to notice that the Total early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity (TEA) lag in one year has a significant effect on the present rate; this evidence implies that the choice of a given individual by entrepreneurship as a career option affects the future decision of new individuals through entrepreneurship.

This result corroborates the considerations of Lundström and Stevenson (2006) regarding exposure to entrepreneurship, which points to the positive effect of entering entrepreneurs in the market for visibility and encouragement of new decisions to be carried out. In addition, a more significant number of entrepreneurs in society tends to favor the promotion of entrepreneurial values and the acceptance of entrepreneurship among individuals (Casson, 2010; Wildeman *et al.*, 1999; Wilken, 1979).

Both regressions, which bring the motivations for opportunity (OE) and necessity (NE), also present significant coefficients to explain the current entrepreneurship rate. Such evidence implies that the inertia of the entrepreneurship rate occurs regardless of the reasons for assuming it. Individuals tend to opt for entrepreneurship as a career. Others have made that choice either because they have found an opportunity in the market or because of the need for subsistence.

Considering the economic variables, per capita income's role in explaining the variation of entrepreneurship rates in the Brazilian states is highlighted. On the effect of this determinant on entrepreneurship, Verheul *et al.* (2002) emphasize its impact on technological development, industrial structure, and especially on the expansion of demand for products and services, creating opportunities for entrepreneurship.

The GDP per capita in its lags is one of the variables that most explain the variation in the entrepreneurship rates included in the regressions. All the lags were significant at five and ten percent. This evidence is in line with the results of Melo *et al.* (2000) and Stel *et al.* (2003), who found no empirical evidence for the effect of GDP per capita and the tax burden on the present study results.

The GDP per capita variable, in turn, has an oscillating effect on entrepreneurship, changing its relation between positive and negative, according to the discrepancy applied in the model. One hypothesis for this behavior would be the role of individual memory regarding the variations of the economic growth that it involves, making it possible to notice that in all the rates under analysis, the second lag presents the greater potential of positive influence on the rate of current entrepreneurship, indicating that the second-year lag has a greater effect on the memory of individuals.

It is also worth mentioning that the per capita GDP variation tends to have more significant effects on entrepreneurship by opportunity (OE) than by necessity (NE). This result corroborates the concepts of these motivations to be accomplished (Fuentelsaz *et al.*, 2015, Urbano & Aparicio, 2016).

Once it has been pointed out that per capita income is apt to affect the demand for products and services, its potential effect on the opportunities to fulfill is evident, thus explaining the variation in the rate of entrepreneurship by opportunity (OE). The creation of enterprises by necessity tends to be less dependent on the demand for products and services due to the imminent character of the business.

The unemployment rate is expected to be significant and with a considerable explanatory ratio, especially on the rate of Necessity Entrepreneurship (NE), when there are no occupancy options. The study of Melo *et al.* (2015) indicates a positive and significant relationship on entrepreneurship, other authors, such as Stel *et al.* (2003), Ovaska and Sobel (2005), contradict their results, pointing to a non-significant effect of unemployment on the opening of new companies.

In turn, it is possible to perceive in the present study that, in most of the estimates of the effect of the unemployment rate on entrepreneurship, there are non-significant results, with coefficients in small proportions. This relationship was significant at ten percent in the third leg of the unemployment rate, which positively affects the rate of opportunity entrepreneurship. Substantial and negative values are also presented for a one-year lag for Necessity Entrepreneurship (NE), two years for Opportunity Entrepreneurship (OE), and significant. These results may indicate a preference of the individuals for the salaried career, in comparison to the option to be achieved, even in the case of necessity. Further revealing that if unemployment has occurred in more recent periods, it may still generate interest in the individual to return to the labor market and

become disinterested in the undertaking. For more extended periods, that interest may have disappeared as a result. Another explanatory hypothesis of this context can be formulated when considering the effect of social security on the options to be undertaken in unemployment.

Verheul *et al.* (2002) point to an adverse effect of social security policies on the entrepreneurship level of the countries. Higher levels of social security, especially in a period of unemployment, tend to increase the opportunity cost to assume, making entrepreneurial activity comparatively less attractive.

Positive and significant signaling of the effect of unemployment on opportunity entrepreneurship may be associated with situations where people insured during the unemployment period opt for entrepreneurial activity after identifying a latent opportunity for products or services in the market.

Regarding the institutional variables, the tax burden's essential role is highlighted to explain the variation of the Total early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity and Necessity Entrepreneurship (TEA, NE). The tax burden presented the largest significant coefficients among other explanatory variables. This result is in line with the conclusions of Melo *et al.* (2015) and Stel *et al.* (2003), who did not find empirical evidence on the effect of the tax burden on the opening of new firms.

The tax burden has a considerably negative effect on entrepreneurship rates and is a potentially discouraging factor for entrepreneurial activity in the Brazilian states. This variable is significant in the current period, indicating that the effect of taxes on entrepreneurship occurs precisely in the year they affect firms' opening and development.

Necessity Entrepreneurship (NE) rates are more sensitive to variations in the tax burden compared to Opportunity Entrepreneurship (OE), which was not significant; a possible explanation for this phenomenon is the low financial resources involved in the opening of enterprises due to subsistence (Morris *et al.*, 2018; Morris *et al.*, 2015), it is possible to question whether this relationship evidenced in the estimated models contributes to the increase of the Brazilian informal market.

About the total credit operations of the financial system for individuals, there is a behavior that reinforces the results of Melo *et al.* (2015) and Ovaska and Sobel (2005). The variable was statistically significant for the entrepreneurship rates in their multiple dimensions (TEA, OE and NE), exerting low potential of effect on these dependent variables. The coefficients' signals vary from positive for TEA and NE regression and negative for OE regression. Possible explanations for this result may be related to the context of credit operations. This variable is composed of several loan balances for individuals. The positive effect of access to credit on the initial entrepreneurship rate may be related to the implications of this variable on demand for products and services. For entrepreneurship, by necessity, the opening of credit can be an impetus to the beginning of the entrepreneurial process, given the financial difficulties in which the individual may be passing. However, the negative relation of this variable to entrepreneurship by opportunity may be related to the level of default by individuals for the period under analysis.

Among the cultural variables, there were no significant results. Higher educational levels would theoretically positively affect entrepreneurship levels in Brazilian states (Fuentelsaz *et al.*, 2015; Wennekers *et al.*, 2002).

In turn, the effects of corruption are contradictory, e.g., Melo *et al.* (2015) found a positive relationship between entrepreneurship and bureaucratic corruption in Brazilian states. This counterintuitive result for theory would be related to the high bureaucratic obstacles present during opening and developing companies, making corruption a positive influence on opening new businesses.

When observed in the Brazilian regions, it is noted that only the Northeast region presented significance, only influencing the Total early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity and Opportunity Entrepreneurship. These results may reflect the historical development process in Brazil. Since the region had a late development process (Diniz, 2002) and the possible saturation of ventures in the South and Southeast regions, new opportunities to undertake can be found in the Northeast, favoring its regional development.

Conclusions

The present study analyzed the institutional, cultural, and economic factors that tend to differentiate entrepreneurial activity among Brazilian states. In this paper, empirical evidence was found to support the argument that the average initial entrepreneurship rate in Brazil is made up in large proportions by enterprising entrepreneurs in the markets of the South and Southeast regions.

The period under analysis points to a concentration of average rates of entrepreneurship among Brazilian regions, with the four worst average entrepreneurship rates coming from states in the country's northern region. The identification of determinants of entrepreneurship contributes to the understanding of these regional discrepancies.

According to the regressions estimated in the present study, Brazilian entrepreneurship can be better explained by formal economic and institutional factors than by cultural variables. In this sense, states with higher per capita income and lower tax burdens tend to stimulate initial entrepreneurship rates and their composition by necessity and opportunity. The effects of unemployment rates and credit operations on the financial market lean towards having little influence on entrepreneurship in the Brazilian states.

The discovered results contribute to the literature in contemplating the multidimensionality of entrepreneurship, which, having determinants from different spheres of analysis, invite the research to relate interdisciplinary factors to advance the understanding of this phenomenon. The contributions of this study were based on the decomposition of entrepreneurship rates in terms of their motivations to assume, given the different realities of the Brazilian states.

The aspects emphasized in this research indicate ways of thinking about public policies to promote entrepreneurship, which should not only consider factors stimulating this phenomenon but also efforts to inhibit strong elements of discouragement to entrepreneurship (Emmendoerfer et al., 2021), especially in emerging economic sectors, such as high tax burden among Brazilian states. It is also important to understand the regional demands to develop the regions, bearing in mind their cultural, political, economic, and environmental characteristics, to minimize inequalities and improve social conditions. In addition, the importance of a sustained growth economy is highlighted for a broader manifestation of free enterprise through entrepreneurship, including in emerging markets and productive sectors such as the creative economy (Fioravante & Emmendoerfer, 2019).

This study provides the basis for future research that expands the models' explanatory capacity by including descriptive elements for entrepreneurship in Brazil. Advancements regarding the main aspects that differentiate the level of entrepreneurial activity between the Brazilian states are promising for a better understanding of this complex reality and susceptible to new approaches and contributions.

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